

Privacy concerns and self-efficacy in e-commerce: Testing an extended APCO model in a prototypical EU country

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ABSTRACT

Privacy concerns are an important factor in internet users' decisions to participate in e-commerce, defined here as the use of the internet by individuals to purchase goods or services. While various studies have examined how privacy concerns and e-commerce participation are influenced by online shopping self-efficacy, personality traits, or demographic characteristics, these aspects have rarely been examined together in one single explanatory model. Therefore, this paper proposes an integrated model of e-commerce participation based on the APCO model (Antecedents, Privacy Concerns, Outcomes; Smith et al., 2011) in which internet users' personality traits and demographic characteristics influence their privacy concerns and online shopping self-efficacy, which in turn affect e-commerce participation. The model was tested on a sample of internet users ($n = 3,736$) in Slovenia, a prototypical EU country in terms of internet use and online shopping. The results from path analysis showed that individuals with greater privacy concerns were less likely to participate in e-commerce, while those with higher online shopping self-efficacy were more likely to do so. Online shopping self-efficacy also reduced privacy concerns and mediated the effect of demographic characteristics on privacy concerns and e-commerce participation. Therefore, a viable strategy to increase e-commerce participation is to increase internet users' self-efficacy. Moreover, users with different personalities seem to have different coping strategies related to privacy concerns and online shopping self-efficacy. Overall, this study highlights the importance of online shopping self-efficacy for comprehensively analyzing the antecedents and outcomes of privacy concerns in e-commerce.

1. Introduction

The internet has become a major shopping channel through which consumers can obtain a range of benefits, including increased access to information, lower product costs, convenience, avoidance of intermediaries, and a greater variety of goods and services (Cai and Cude, 2016). Moreover, companies benefit by coming into direct contact with consumers and collecting extensive data about their website visits, product preferences, and purchasing behaviors (Laudon and Traver, 2016; Neudecker et al., 2015). Although such data help companies in their marketing activities (Neudecker et al., 2015), their collection and use can also raise privacy concerns (Bandara et al., 2020a; Wirtz et al., 2007). This may make consumers reluctant to engage in e-commerce activities (Marchany and Tront, 2002; Wirtz et al., 2007). For example, Auxier et al. (2019) reported that 81% of Americans feel they have little knowledge or control over companies' data collection practices.

Similarly, Bandara et al. (2020b) found that individuals are often unaware of how information submitted in e-commerce transactions is used by online retailers. This is problematic because privacy concerns are a major reason that deters consumers from shopping online (Cai and Cude, 2016).

Although the importance of privacy concerns has been recognized, their predictors and influence on behavior have been investigated in a disjoint manner (Rohunen et al., 2020; Scarpi et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2011). For example, there are very few replications of existing results (Smith et al., 2011), theoretical models are built in an *ad hoc* and eclectic manner (Rohunen et al., 2020), and some variables are understood as predictors at one time and as consequences of privacy concerns at another (Scarpi et al., 2022; Yun et al., 2019). Given this situation, it has recently been suggested that what is needed is not to examine new determinants of privacy concerns but to combine the results of previous studies and comprehensively investigate these relationships (Bandara

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Fig. 1. Proposed explanatory model of e-commerce participation according to the APCO model.

et al., 2020a; Scarpi et al., 2022; Yun et al., 2019).

Numerous theories have been adopted to explain the influence of privacy concerns on behavior (Li, 2011; Rohunen et al., 2020). However, many of these provide only loose starting points because “they do not explicitly define the roles and the relationships among different privacy behavior variables” (Rohunen et al., 2020, p. 387). In contrast, the *antecedents, privacy concerns, and outcomes* (APCO) model explicitly positions individual characteristics (e.g., demographics, personality, internet use, and skills) as antecedents to privacy concerns and intentions and behavioral reactions as their consequences (Smith et al., 2011). Therefore, it is a useful framework to comprehensively examine the role of privacy concerns in internet users’ behavior.

One drawback of the APCO model, however, is that it focuses on privacy concerns as the sole mediator between internet users’ characteristics and behaviors. Many studies have shown the importance of internet users’ actual or perceived internet skills in privacy-related behavior (Akhter, 2014; Büchi et al., 2017; Dinev and Hart, 2005; Hong et al., 2021). On the one hand, internet skills reduce privacy concerns, as more skilled users are better able to protect their privacy (Epstein and Quinn, 2020; Park, 2013). On the other hand, they are crucial to conducting online activities (Litt, 2013; van Deursen et al., 2017). For instance, Dinev and Hart (2005) found that higher levels of internet literacy reduce privacy concerns and increase intention to transact. Relatedly, Akhter (2014) showed that internet self-efficacy, defined as confidence in one’s ability to use the internet, reduces privacy concerns and increases the frequency of online transactions. Epstein and Quinn (2020) noted that similar factors that influence privacy concerns in the APCO model are also factors that influence internet-related skills.

With respect to e-commerce, recent studies have provided thorough accounts of how privacy concerns, internet skills, and demographics influence e-commerce participation (Alkis and Kose, 2022; Garín-Muñoz et al., 2019; Kose and Arslan, 2020). However, these studies have not considered demographic characteristics as potential antecedents of privacy concerns and internet skills or their indirect influence on e-commerce participation. In addition, scholars have not investigated the role of internet users’ personality, which has an important influence on privacy concerns (Benamati et al., 2017; Korzaan and Boswell, 2008; Osatuyi, 2015). Examining the interrelationships among these variables is important because some may no longer hold, as they are mediated by other factors. For instance, while some studies have indicated that

privacy concerns increase with age (Benamati et al., 2017; Joinson et al., 2010), the literature suggests that internet skills mediate the effect of age on privacy concerns. Namely, older internet users, who tend to have lower internet skills (Litt, 2013), perceive more privacy threats because they are unfamiliar with the online environment (Akhter, 2014; Dinev and Hart, 2005).

Against this backdrop, this study built on the APCO model to propose and test an original explanatory model in which privacy concerns and online shopping self-efficacy, a form of perceived internet skills (Litt, 2013), mediate between the antecedents (i.e., demographic characteristics, personality traits, and internet experiences) and outcomes (i.e., e-commerce participation) in the APCO model (Fig. 1). The proposed model was tested empirically with path analysis on data collected in 2020 with a web survey of Slovenian internet users ($n = 3,736$). Slovenia is a prototypical European Union (EU) country in terms of internet use and online shopping (Eurostat, 2022), which strengthens the generalizability of our findings. In 2021, 89% of Slovenians used the internet in the last three months (EU average: 89%), while 59% shopped online (EU average: 57%). Therefore, the current study provides interesting insights into the European situation.

In the next section, the conceptual justification for the model is presented and hypotheses are posed. A description of the methods and procedures is then provided, followed by a presentation of the results. Next, the main findings are discussed, together with recommendations for practitioners. This is followed by a proposal of possible new research avenues and a discussion of the study limitations. The last section concludes the paper.

2. Conceptual framework

2.1. E-commerce participation

E-commerce participation has various definitions, including buying or selling products, both, or participating in other marketing activities (Kose and Arslan, 2020; Luo and Niu, 2019). However, in the context of online shopping, e-commerce participation can be defined as the use of the internet by individuals to purchase goods or services (Alkis and Kose, 2022; Garín-Muñoz et al., 2019; Kose and Arslan, 2020). Although participation in e-commerce can bring several benefits, such as convenience, increased variety of goods, and lower prices (Monsuwé et al., 2004), a significant proportion of internet users are reluctant to shop

Table 1
Effects of personality traits on privacy concerns in the literature.

Source	Country	Context	N	E	A	C	N	O
Junglas et al. (2008)	US	Location-based services	378		-	+		+
Korzaan and Boswell (2008)	US	General internet use	230		+			
Osatuyi (2015)	US	Social media	298		+	+		
Bansal et al. (2016)	US	Finance	367		+		+	
	US	E-commerce	367	-	+		+	
	US	Health	367		+		+	
Pentina et al. (2016)	US	Mobile apps	106					
	China	Mobile apps	120					
Chen et al. (2017)	Vietnam	Social network sites	298	-	+	+		+
Yeh et al. (2018)	Taiwan	E-commerce	345		+			
Özkan (2018)	Turkey	General internet use	402	-		+		+
Škrinjaric et al. (2018)	Croatia	General internet use	2,060	-			+	
van der Schyff et al. (2020)	/	Social network sites	576			+	+	+
Bawack et al. (2021)	US	Voice shopping	224				-	
Tang et al. (2022)	China	Mobile apps	455		+	+	+	

Notes. E = Extraversion; A = Agreeableness; C = Conscientiousness; N = Neuroticism; O = Openness; + = significant positive relationship; - = significant negative relationship; empty cells = no significant relationship or significance not reported; / = not reported.

online. While past research has suggested that this is due to differences in individual characteristics, such as demographics or level of internet use, scholars have increasingly identified privacy concerns and lack of confidence in the ability to make an online purchase as key issues preventing e-commerce participation (Alkis and Kose, 2022; Cai and Cude, 2016; Dinev and Hart, 2005; van Deursen et al., 2017).

2.2. Privacy concerns

Privacy concerns in the context of online shopping refer to internet users' beliefs regarding how their information submitted during e-commerce transactions will be handled (Bélanger and Crossler, 2011; Dinev and Hart, 2006). These concerns can also be considered part of the online shopping risk (Dinev and Hart, 2006). As the online shopping environment differs from the offline shopping environment in that consumers have less information about the vendor or product (Kim and Forsythe, 2008), online shoppers may experience greater uncertainty and risk due to asymmetric information. This, in turn, affects their online purchasing decisions. Studies have indicated that users who are more concerned about privacy are less likely to participate in e-commerce (Akhter, 2014; Alkis and Kose, 2022; Dinev and Hart, 2005; Garín-Muñoz et al., 2019). Therefore, we hypothesize:

H1: Privacy concerns have a negative effect on e-commerce participation.

2.3. Online shopping self-efficacy

In general, self-efficacy refers to the confidence one has in being able to perform a particular action (Bandura, 1977). Accordingly, online shopping self-efficacy can be considered as the level of confidence that internet users have in their ability to successfully make an online purchase (Dash and Saji, 2008). Since individuals tend to engage in behaviors that they believe are under their control, self-efficacy influences their choice of behavior (Bandura, 1977). Consequently, internet users with higher self-efficacy in online shopping can be expected to make more online purchases (Akhter, 2014; Eastin, 2002; San-Martín et al., 2020). Online shopping self-efficacy can also be considered an important antecedent of privacy concerns. We can assume that consumers who are more confident in their ability to shop online believe that they have greater control over all aspects of the purchase process, including their privacy. In fact, research has demonstrated that highly skilled internet users have lower privacy concerns (Akhter, 2014; Büchi et al., 2017; Dinev and Hart, 2005). Based on these considerations, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H2: Online shopping self-efficacy positively affects e-commerce participation.

H3: Online shopping self-efficacy negatively affects privacy concerns.

2.4. Internet uses

Internet uses refer to the breadth of actions performed over the internet (Blank and Groselj, 2014). Engagement with a wider array of internet platforms and services familiarizes users with different forms of digital engagement (Helsper, 2021) and consequently reduces the additional cognitive demands required to learn and master new or complex activities, such as conducting online shopping transactions (Naseri and Elliott, 2011). Thus, it is reasonable to expect that internet uses increase confidence in one's ability to shop online (Eastin and LaRose, 2006). Research has also shown that users who engage in a broader set of internet activities are more likely to participate in e-commerce (Helsper and Eynon, 2010; Naseri and Elliott, 2011). Hence, we propose the following:

H4: Internet uses have a positive effect on online shopping self-efficacy.

H5: Internet uses have a positive effect on e-commerce participation.

2.5. Personality traits

The personality of internet users can be a strong predictor of their perceptions, abilities, and intentions (Bosnjak et al., 2007; Correa et al., 2010; San-Martín et al., 2020). Personality is often studied by assessing various personality traits (John and Srivastava, 1999), which are considered relatively stable patterns of individuals' thinking or behaving (Soto, 2018). While there are many approaches to delineating these traits, one of the most common and widely accepted taxonomies is the Big Five model of personality (John and Srivastava, 1999; McCrae and Costa, 1987), which is based on extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness (McCrae and Costa, 1987).

Extraversion is associated with sociability, friendliness, and talkativeness as well as dominance and assertiveness. Agreeableness can be viewed in contrast to antagonism, and antagonistic individuals tend to be distrustful, skeptical, and uncooperative (McCrae and Costa, 1987). Therefore, agreeableness is related to trust and cooperativeness. Individuals who are conscientious are well organized, goal oriented, and capable of self-discipline. Conversely, neurotic individuals are emotionally unstable and tend to worry a lot. Openness refers to being open to new experiences, imaginative, original, and daring (McCrae and Costa, 1987).

2.5.1. Personality traits and privacy concerns

Past research has shown that personality traits influence privacy concerns. However, the results regarding which traits are important are mixed (Table 1). For example, Junglas et al. (2008) found that agreeableness decreased, whereas conscientiousness and openness increased privacy concerns. Conversely, Bansal et al. (2016) showed that extraversion decreased while agreeableness and neuroticism increased privacy concerns; however, conscientiousness and openness had no significant effect. Although some differences may be due to contextual or cultural variations (Nissenbaum, 2010), there seems to be some convergent evidence in the literature: extraversion generally decreases privacy concerns, while agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness increase them (Table 1). Accordingly, we tested the following hypotheses:

- H6a: Extraversion has a negative effect on privacy concerns.
- H6b: Agreeableness has a positive effect on privacy concerns.
- H6c: Conscientiousness has a positive effect on privacy concerns.
- H6d: Neuroticism has a positive effect on privacy concerns.
- H6e: Openness has a positive effect on privacy concerns.

2.5.2. Personality traits and online shopping self-efficacy

Personality traits were also shown to influence self-efficacy. While many studies have examined the influence of personality traits on self-efficacy (Barańczuk, 2021), we found only one focusing specifically on online shopping self-efficacy (San-Martín et al., 2020). The results suggested that neuroticism was negatively associated with online shopping self-efficacy, whereas extraversion and openness were positively associated. Agreeableness and conscientiousness were not associated with online shopping self-efficacy. Although self-efficacy is an action-specific concept (Bandura, 1977), these results are largely in line with meta-analyses of the association between personality traits and various forms of self-efficacy (e.g., generalized self-efficacy or creative self-efficacy), which have shown that neuroticism is negatively associated with self-efficacy, while extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness are positively associated with self-efficacy (Barańczuk, 2021; Karwowski and Lebeda, 2016). Based on this evidence, we propose the following hypotheses:

- H7a: Extraversion has a positive effect on online shopping self-efficacy.
- H7b: Agreeableness has a positive effect on online shopping self-efficacy.
- H7c: Conscientiousness has a positive effect on online shopping self-efficacy.
- H7d: Neuroticism has a negative effect on online shopping self-efficacy.
- H7e: Openness has a positive effect on online shopping self-efficacy.

2.6. Demographics

Demographic characteristics influence internet-related perceptions and behaviors not only because of users' social roles and interests (Kalmus et al., 2011), but also because the associated offline social and economic disadvantages can result in online inequalities (van Dijk, 2005). Research has shown differences between gender, age, educational, and income groups in relation to privacy concerns (Benamati et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2016; Proudfoot et al., 2018), internet skills (Litt, 2013), and the likelihood of being an online shopper (Alkis and Kose, 2022; Garín-Muñoz et al., 2019). Therefore, we propose the following:

- H8: (a) Gender, (b) age, (c) education, and (d) income influence privacy concerns.
- H9: (a) Gender, (b) age, (c) education, and (d) income influence online shopping self-efficacy.

Table 2
Demographic characteristics of the sample (weighted data).

Variable	Value	Total sample (%) ^a
Gender	Male	53.1
	Female	46.9
Age ^b	18–24	11.9
	25–34	21.4
	35–44	17.9
	45–54	24.8
	55–65	23.9
Education	Primary basic education or lower	4.2
	Vocational or technical secondary education	14.7
	General upper secondary education	53.0
	Higher professional education	9.3
Income ^c	Bachelor or higher education	18.8
	Well below average	17.9
	Slightly below average	38.8
	Similar to average	32.2
	Slightly above average	10.4
E-commerce participation ^d	Well above average	0.8
	Within the last week	26.4
	Within the last month	28.5
	Within the last 3 months	16.5
	Within the last 12 months	10.9
	More than 12 months ago	7.5
Never	10.3	

Notes: ^a n = 3,736. Percentage totals per variable may not add to 100 due to rounding and non-response. ^b M = 42.7 years, SD = 13.5. ^c This is a subjective measure in which respondents indicate how much their income differs from the national average. ^d 71.3% had shopped online in the last three months.

H10: (a) Gender, (b) age, (c) education, and (d) income influence e-commerce participation.

3. Method

3.1. Data collection and survey design

The proposed model was tested on a sample of Slovenian internet users aged between 18 and 65 years. The respondents were recruited from the largest Slovenian access panel (held by Valicon, a member of ESOMAR), while the data collection was conducted at the University of Ljubljana using 1KA software (<https://oneclicksurvey.com/>), an open-source web survey software tool. To obtain a sample reflecting the structure of the target population, groups with higher nonresponse (e.g., males, uneducated, and older) were initially oversampled, which was additionally corrected with quota selection according to gender, age, income, education, and region.

The survey was fielded in January and February 2020. A total of 11,169 people were invited, and 4,771 started the survey (participation rate: 43%). Of these, 713 respondents did not complete the questionnaire and were therefore excluded from the sample. A further 311 respondents were excluded due to missing values on variables of interest, while 11 were excluded due to indicating their age as over 65. The characteristics of the final sample (n = 3,736), weighted with post-stratification weights, are presented in Table 2. The dataset and codebook are available at <https://doi.org/10.23668/psycharchives.5107>.

Table 3
Descriptive statistics of items used in the analysis (weighted data).

	Mean	Standard deviation	Min.	Max.	Skewness	Kurtosis
1. E-commerce participation	0.71	0.45	0	1	-0.94	-1.11
2. Privacy concerns	3.26	1.06	1	5	-0.24	-0.56
3. Online shopping self-efficacy	3.86	1.15	1	5	-0.78	-0.31
4. Internet uses	8.34	1.66	0	10	-1.11	1.01
5. Extraversion	2.99	0.75	1	5	-0.07	-0.09
6. Agreeableness	3.49	0.61	1	5	-0.14	0.35
7. Conscientiousness	3.68	0.71	1	5	-0.32	0.04
8. Neuroticism	2.85	0.68	1	5	0.10	0.06
9. Openness	3.27	0.68	1	5	0.11	0.01

3.2. Measures

E-commerce participation was measured by asking respondents “When did you last buy or order goods or services over the internet (e.g. products from Amazon, flights, hotel bookings, tickets, clothes, food ...)?” The respondents indicated whether they had purchased or ordered anything online within the last week, last month, last 3 months, last 12 months, more than 12 months ago, or if they never purchased or ordered anything online. The responses were dichotomized, with 1 representing respondents who made an online purchase/order in the last 3 months, and 0 representing respondents who did not. The cut-off point of 3 months was chosen as it is often used to differentiate between users and non-users of the internet or online services (Eurostat, 2022; Garín-Muñoz et al., 2019).

Privacy concerns were defined as perceptions of the possible misuse of one’s information submitted in the context of online shopping (Bélanger and Crossler, 2011). They were measured with a single item that asked the respondents to indicate their agreement with the statement “I am concerned about the privacy of personal data while shopping online” on a five-point scale (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*).

Online shopping self-efficacy was defined as an individual’s confidence in their ability to successfully complete an online purchase (Dash and Saji, 2008). It was measured with a single item: “I lack the necessary digital skills to shop online” (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*). The responses were reversed for the analysis; thus, higher values expressed greater self-efficacy.

Internet uses were measured as the breadth of internet uses (i.e., the number of different online actions performed on the internet) (Blank and Grošelj, 2014; Reisdorf et al., 2021). They were assessed by asking the respondents whether they had performed any of the 10 activities (Appendix 1, Table A1) using (a) a desktop computer, (b) a mobile phone, (c) both, or (d) did not perform that specific activity. To obtain an index of internet uses, these variables were recoded into a dichotomous form (i.e., performed on any device versus not performed at all) and then summed. The internal consistency of the score was not calculated because the measure is considered a formative construct (Reisdorf et al., 2021).

Table 4
Correlation matrix (weighted data).

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.
1. E-commerce participation	1.00												
2. Privacy concerns	-0.24	1.00											
3. Online shopping self-efficacy	0.35	-0.36	1.00										
4. Internet uses	0.30	-0.11	0.24	1.00									
5. Extraversion	0.01 ^{NS}	-0.06	0.03 ^{NS}	0.13	1.00								
6. Agreeableness	0.00 ^{NS}	0.01 ^{NS}	0.06	0.08	0.29	1.00							
7. Conscientiousness	-0.03 ^{NS}	0.05	0.03	-0.04	0.13	0.11	1.00						
8. Neuroticism	-0.03 ^{NS}	0.06	-0.11	0.00 ^{NS}	-0.22	-0.06	-0.16	1.00					
9. Openness	0.16	-0.06	0.24	0.16	0.18	0.25	-0.02 ^{NS}	-0.07	1.00				
10. Gender	-0.07	0.12	-0.14	-0.02 ^{NS}	0.02 ^{NS}	0.21	0.07	0.10	-0.04	1.00			
11. Age	-0.19	0.13	-0.26	-0.30	0.05	0.02 ^{NS}	0.18	-0.12	-0.20	0.04	1.00		
12. Education	0.18	-0.04	0.18	0.16	-0.02 ^{NS}	0.08	0.05	-0.06	0.19	0.08	-0.14	1.00	
13. Income	0.09	-0.06	0.13	0.10	0.08	0.02 ^{NS}	0.01 ^{NS}	-0.12	0.08	-0.13	0.01 ^{NS}	0.31	1.00

Notes: Significant at $p < 0.05$; ^{NS} = non-significant correlation.

Personality traits. The items measuring the traits from the Big Five personality model were taken from the Mini International Personality Item Pool (Donnellan et al., 2006). This battery contains 20 items that describe various behaviors, and the respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which the statements accurately described them. The response options were on a five-point scale ranging from 1 = *very inaccurate* to 5 = *very accurate*. The items were used in their original form and order. To validate the five-factor personality model, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted (the items and EFA are described in Appendix 2). All items, except one, loaded on the intended factors. After the deletion of the problematic item (“Make a mess of things”), a five-factor solution was obtained with Cronbach’s alpha ranging from 0.679 to 0.773. The items for each factor were averaged to obtain a score for each trait (Donnellan et al., 2006).

The *demographic variables* were gender, age, education, and income. Gender was measured as a binary variable (0 = *male* and 1 = *female*), age as a continuous variable indicating the respondent’s age in years at the time of the survey, and education and income as ordinal scale variables. See Table 2 for the response categories.

3.3. Data analysis

The model was tested by conducting path analysis in R (R Core Team, 2022) with the package *lavaan* (Rosseel, 2012). Path analysis was used because it tests whether the associations between the variables in a given dataset reflect theoretically defined causal relationships between the variables specified in the model (Lleras, 2005). Given that the main dependent variable (e-commerce participation) was dichotomous, we used the mean- and variance-adjusted weighted least squares (WLSMV) estimator (Finney and DiStefano, 2013). As this produced probit coefficients for all paths influencing the dichotomous dependent variable, we also transformed them into logit coefficients and then computed odds ratios (OR) for easier interpretation. Although the scaling factor for transforming probit coefficients into logit coefficients is not constant, a factor of 1.7 has been suggested as a good approximation (Finney and DiStefano, 2013; Kline, 2015). Thus, the OR were calculated as $OR = \exp(b \cdot 1.7)$. Post-stratification weights were applied in all analyses.

$\chi^2_{(df)} = 21.247_{(6)}$; CFI = 0.969; TLI = 0.984; RMSEA [90% CI] = 0.026 [0.015–0.039]; SRMR = 0.003; R² = coefficient of determination

Fig. 2. Results of path analysis (weighted data). The figure shows the unstandardized coefficients. The path coefficients on e-commerce participation are probit coefficients. Only solid lines are significant at $p < 0.05$.

4. Results

We first present the descriptive statistics for the included variables (Table 3).

We also examined bivariate relationships (Table 4). Most of the correlations were statistically significant, although the correlations were generally weak ($-0.36 \leq r \leq 0.35$). The directions of the correlations between the internet-related variables were as expected. Namely, there were positive correlations among e-commerce participation, online shopping self-efficacy, and internet uses, while privacy concerns were negatively correlated with these three variables. Interestingly, the correlations between personality traits and internet-related variables were all weak, sometimes even non-significant, except for openness, which was correlated with all four internet-related variables. Among the demographic variables, age generally had the highest (in absolute terms) correlation with internet-related and personality variables.

Next, we proceeded with the model estimation. According to the standards for acceptable values of fit indices (Kline, 2015), the model indicated an adequate fit to the data ($\chi^2_{(df)} = 21.247_{(6)}$; CFI = 0.969; TLI = 0.984; RMSEA [90% CI] = 0.026 [0.015–0.039]; SRMR = 0.003).

The results of the path analysis are summarized in Fig. 2 and Table 5. The results confirmed the hypotheses that users with higher privacy concerns were less likely to participate in e-commerce ($OR = 0.745, p \leq 0.001$), while those with higher online shopping self-efficacy ($OR = 1.563, p \leq 0.001$) and more varied internet uses ($OR = 1.342, p \leq 0.001$) were more likely to participate. In particular, a one-unit increase in privacy concerns decreased the odds of e-commerce participation by 25.5%, whereas a one-unit increase in the online shopping self-efficacy scale or using the internet for an additional activity increased the odds by 56.3% and 34.2%, respectively. Among the demographic characteristics, only education had a significant effect ($OR = 1.269, p \leq 0.001$). Each additional level of education increased the odds of e-commerce participation by 26.9%.

Online shopping self-efficacy was a strong predictor of privacy concerns ($\beta = -0.352, p \leq 0.001$). Personality traits that had a statistically significant influence on privacy concerns were extraversion ($\beta = -0.071, p \leq 0.001$), conscientiousness ($\beta = 0.059, p \leq 0.001$), and openness ($\beta =$

$0.044, p = 0.009$). In contrast, the hypothesized effects of agreeableness and neuroticism could not be confirmed. The only demographic variable affecting privacy concerns was gender ($\beta = 0.064, p \leq 0.001$), with females being slightly more concerned than males.

In the case of online shopping self-efficacy, the results confirmed that users with a broader set of internet uses have greater self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.140, p \leq 0.001$). Moreover, conscientiousness ($\beta = 0.067, p \leq 0.001$) and openness ($\beta = 0.154, p \leq 0.001$) increased, whereas neuroticism decreased ($\beta = -0.098, p \leq 0.001$) online shopping self-efficacy. The effect of agreeableness could not be confirmed. Interestingly, the effect of extraversion was statistically significant but in the opposite direction than hypothesized ($\beta = -0.050, p = 0.007$). The results also confirmed the influence of all four demographic characteristics on online shopping self-efficacy. Older individuals ($\beta = -0.202, p \leq 0.001$) and females ($\beta = -0.121, p \leq 0.001$) had lower online shopping self-efficacy, while more educated ($\beta = 0.079, p \leq 0.001$) and those with higher income ($\beta = 0.053, p = 0.003$) had higher self-efficacy.

5. Discussion

5.1. General discussion

This study built on the original APCO model (Smith et al., 2011) to comprehensively examine the relationships among privacy concerns, online shopping self-efficacy, and e-commerce participation and determine how these variables are influenced by personality traits and demographic characteristics. The analysis validated the proposed model and demonstrated the value of comprehensively examining the antecedents to e-commerce participation.

The results showed that those with higher privacy concerns were less likely to participate in e-commerce (H1), while those with higher online shopping self-efficacy were more likely to participate (H2). Moreover, those with increased engagement with the internet were more likely to participate in e-commerce (H5). Interestingly, among the demographic characteristics, only education influenced the likelihood of e-commerce participation (H10c). The absence of direct effects of gender (H10a), age (H10b), and income (H10d) on e-commerce participation is contrary to

Table 5
Summary of regression test outcomes.

#	Hypothesis	Estimate	Standard error	p	Validation
H1	Privacy concerns → E-commerce participation	-0.173	0.024	<0.001	Yes
H2	Online shopping self-efficacy → E-commerce participation	0.263	0.022	<0.001	Yes
H3	Online shopping self-efficacy → Privacy concerns	-0.324	0.017	<0.001	Yes
H4	Internet uses → Online shopping self-efficacy	0.098	0.013	<0.001	Yes
H5	Internet uses → E-commerce participation	0.173	0.016	<0.001	Yes
H6a	Extraversion → Privacy concerns	-0.100	0.025	<0.001	Yes
H6b	Agreeableness → Privacy concerns	0.046	0.029	0.120	No
H6c	Conscientiousness → Privacy concerns	0.089	0.025	0.000	Yes
H6d	Neuroticism → Privacy concerns	0.021	0.026	0.427	No
H6e	Openness → Privacy concerns	0.069	0.027	0.009	Yes
H7a	Extraversion → Online shopping self-efficacy	-0.077	0.029	0.007	Inverted
H7b	Agreeableness → Online shopping self-efficacy	0.061	0.034	0.074	No
H7c	Conscientiousness → Online shopping self-efficacy	0.109	0.028	<0.001	Yes
H7d	Neuroticism → Online shopping self-efficacy	-0.168	0.030	<0.001	Yes
H7e	Openness → Online shopping self-efficacy	0.262	0.031	<0.001	Yes
H8a	Gender → Privacy concerns	0.136	0.037	<0.001	Yes
H8b	Age → Privacy concerns	0.003	0.002	0.068	No
H8c	Education → Privacy concerns	0.008	0.016	0.623	No
H8d	Income → Privacy concerns	-0.006	0.020	0.785	No
H9a	Gender → Online shopping self-efficacy	-0.280	0.041	<0.001	Yes
H9b	Age → Online shopping self-efficacy	-0.017	0.002	<0.001	Yes
H9c	Education → Online shopping self-efficacy	0.087	0.019	<0.001	Yes
H9d	Income → Online shopping self-efficacy	0.067	0.022	0.003	Yes
H10a	Gender → E-commerce participation	-0.058	0.052	0.264	No
H10b	Age → E-commerce participation	-0.002	0.002	0.382	No
H10c	Education → E-commerce participation	0.140	0.024	<0.001	Yes
H10d	Income → E-commerce participation	0.004	0.029	0.904	No

recent studies (Alkis and Kose, 2022; Garín-Muñoz et al., 2019). However, these studies did not examine privacy concerns or online shopping self-efficacy as mediators between demographic characteristics and e-commerce participation. Indeed, a model with only internet uses and demographic characteristics as predictors of e-commerce participation resulted in internet uses, gender, age, and education having a statistically significant effect ($p \leq 0.001$). An analysis of the indirect effects in the full model (Rijnhart et al., 2019) showed that privacy concerns

mediated only the effect of gender on e-commerce participation ($p = 0.001$) and only 13.8% of the total effect. In contrast, online shopping self-efficacy mediated the effects of all four demographic variables, namely 43.1% of the total effect of gender ($p \leq 0.001$), 58.2% of the total effect of age ($p \leq 0.001$), 22.9% of the total effect of education ($p = \leq 0.001$), and 68.1% of the total effect of income ($p = 0.004$). Taken together, our results indicate the importance of including privacy concerns and especially online shopping self-efficacy as mediators between demographic characteristics and e-commerce participation.

Looking at privacy concerns, the results confirmed that individuals with higher online shopping self-efficacy had lower privacy concerns (H3). The analysis also verified the influence of extraversion (H6a), conscientiousness (H6c), and openness (H6e) on privacy concerns. The negative influence of extraversion is in line with the literature suggesting that because extraverts value social interactions, which often involve sharing personal information, they are less likely to be concerned about their privacy (Bansal et al., 2016; Yeh et al., 2018; Škrinjaric et al., 2018). On the other hand, more conscientious users have higher privacy concerns because they are generally more careful and risk-averse (Junglas et al., 2008; van der Schyff et al., 2020). Interestingly, although some scholars hypothesized openness to decrease privacy concerns since open users are less afraid of risks (Tang et al., 2022; Yeh et al., 2018), our results corroborate the suggestions that openness in fact increases privacy concerns. It has been argued that more open users are generally more inquisitive about technology and possible privacy issues, and therefore have higher privacy concerns (Bansal et al., 2016; Junglas et al., 2008; van der Schyff et al., 2020). Conversely, we could not confirm past findings that more agreeable (H6b) and neurotic (H6d) users have higher privacy concerns. A possible explanation could be the study's setting, as the effects of personality traits on privacy concerns vary considerably by the country or context studied (see Table 1). As these effects have not yet been systematically addressed, a meta-analysis could be a worthwhile research endeavor.

Among the demographic characteristics, privacy concerns were influenced only by gender (H8a). While the effect of gender is in line with the literature, as men and women can have different views on privacy (Petronio, 2002), the absence of the effect of other demographic characteristics contrasts with studies reporting such effects (Benamati et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2016; Proudfoot et al., 2018). However, given the inclusion of self-efficacy in the proposed model, these differences seem plausible. Namely, demographic characteristics often determine individuals' internet experience and proficiency (van Dijk, 2005). Through increased internet experience, self-efficacy can also increase (Eastin and LaRose, 2006), which in turn makes individuals more confident in their ability to manage privacy threats, thereby decreasing privacy concerns (Akhter, 2014). In other words, demographic characteristics, except gender, do not influence privacy concerns directly, but indirectly through self-efficacy. Analysis of indirect effects confirmed that age, education, and income influence privacy concerns through online shopping self-efficacy ($p \leq 0.003$).

In relation to online shopping self-efficacy, the results showed that individuals with a wider set of internet uses had higher online shopping self-efficacy (H4). Moreover, the analysis confirmed the hypothesized positive effects of conscientiousness (H7c) and openness (H7e) and the hypothesized negative effect of neuroticism (H7d) on online shopping self-efficacy. The positive effect of conscientiousness is consistent with the theory of self-efficacy, as only those who persist in threatening activities gain experiences that reinforce their sense of efficacy (Bandura, 1977). Similarly, the tendency of open-minded users to try new things (McCrae and Costa, 1987) might entice them to shop at various online stores, with each successful purchase increasing their self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977). Conversely, since neurotic individuals often worry and are insecure (McCrae and Costa, 1987), it is reasonable to argue that they lack confidence in their ability to shop online. However, we could not confirm the hypothesized positive effects of extraversion (H7a) and agreeableness (H7b) on online shopping self-efficacy. In the case of

extraversion, the effect was in fact negative. Some studies have shown that shy and introverted individuals prefer to use the internet more and see more benefits from it (Ebeling-Witte et al., 2007; Voorn and Komers, 2013). Their increased engagement and favorable attitudes may lead them to believe that they are better able to navigate the online environment. For agreeableness, although past studies have confirmed its positive effects on self-efficacy, these were rather small (Barańczuk, 2021; Karwowski and Lebuda, 2016). Therefore, it is possible that although agreeableness generally influences self-efficacy, its effect on online shopping self-efficacy is negligible (San-Martín et al., 2020).

The significant effects of all four demographic characteristics, namely gender (H9a), age (H9b), education (H9c), and income (H9d), on online shopping self-efficacy corroborate the findings from the digital divide research and, together with the mediating effects of online shopping self-efficacy, demonstrate the seminal role of actual or perceived internet skills for engagement in online activities (Helsper, 2021; van Deursen et al., 2016, 2017).

It is noteworthy that extraversion has a negative influence, whereas conscientiousness and openness have a positive influence on both online shopping self-efficacy and privacy concerns. This is surprising, given that higher levels of online shopping self-efficacy decrease privacy concerns. As the indirect effects of these three personality traits on privacy concerns through self-efficacy were all statistically significant, this suggests that online shopping self-efficacy is a *suppressor* variable (MacKinnon et al., 2000). Such relationships imply that internet users who are less socially oriented, more organized, and open to new experiences generally know more about privacy and the possible abuses related to it, resulting in their higher privacy concerns. However, they mitigate these concerns by being more confident in their abilities, which they have precisely because of their increased proficiency in and experience with the online shopping environment. In contrast, more extraverted, less conscientious, and less open users have lower privacy concerns but also lower self-efficacy, suggesting that they are not as attentive to privacy issues or prone to learning about the online environment. In other words, internet users with different personality traits have different privacy management strategies in e-commerce.

Overall, the results of this study show the importance of online shopping self-efficacy for comprehensive analyses of the antecedents and outcomes of privacy concerns in e-commerce. Its inclusion was crucial, as it was more important than demographic characteristics in predicting individuals' privacy concerns and online shopping. In fact, Hernández et al. (2011) showed that once individuals acquire a certain degree of experience with the online shopping environment, their attitudes and behaviors related to online shopping no longer depend on demographic characteristics. Furthermore, while the current study confirms the usefulness of the APCO model for examining the antecedents and consequences of privacy concerns, it also suggests that its explanatory value could be extended if the mediating role of self-efficacy (or, more generally, internet skills) would be formally included in the model.

5.2. Practical implications

Our results confirmed privacy concerns as a barrier to online shopping (Cai and Cude, 2016). Although internet users shop online despite these concerns (Bandara et al., 2020b), addressing them can help retailers increase their sales (Faja and Trimi, 2006). However, our results indicate that a complementary option for increasing e-commerce participation is to increase internet users' confidence in their ability to

shop online. On the one hand, this would increase participation by decreasing privacy concerns. On the other hand, the effects of demographic characteristics were mediated through online shopping self-efficacy. Therefore, a solution to persuade internet users who shop less is to design interventions that would increase their self-efficacy (e.g., providing interactive help during the online shopping process, guides to adjust their privacy settings, and more options about privacy). With such interventions, the self-efficacy associated with a certain behavior should increase with the successful completion of the corresponding action (Bandura, 1977). Furthermore, companies that implement such activities could benefit from the image of being socially responsible.

Our results also suggest that internet users with different personalities have different coping strategies for dealing with their privacy concerns in online shopping. Thus, online retailers should take this into account in website personalization. Studies on the effects of tailoring information presentation to consumers' personalities have indicated that this can increase purchase intention (Hauser et al., 2009) and decrease privacy concerns and risk perceptions (Schöning et al., 2019). As personality can be inferred from digital traces (Kosinski et al., 2013; Matz and Netzer, 2017), online retailers can use this information to personalize their websites to the personalities of specific consumers. In as much as such inference can lead to privacy concerns, retailers can instead ask their shoppers whether they would like to proceed with default privacy settings or customize them, whether they would like detailed information, and so on. In either case, privacy needs could be better addressed by presenting the related information in a way that best suits each individual's personality.

5.3. Limitations and future work

A certain limitation may arise from the non-probability nature of the access panel sample. However, we used a high-quality access panel, which is also the largest in Slovenia, verified in numerous research projects, including recent government research related to COVID-19 studies (Berzelak et al., 2021). It is formally true that the statistical inference conducted in our analysis is, in principle, possible only with an additional implicit assumption that the data behave as originating from a probability sample, which, however, cannot be verified. Therefore, formally, the inference is clearly subjected to an unknown error arising from departure from probability sampling. However, almost all available research has demonstrated that general marketing research variables, such as those adopted in this study, are robust to such deviations, and the corresponding estimates are close to those from probability samples, which is particularly true for estimates concerning the relationships between the variables and related models (Vehovar et al., 2016). Similarly, the sample reduction caused by missing data might theoretically have some effect on the estimates, but given that the corresponding share was very small, the danger of effects compared to more sophisticated techniques is negligible (Little and Rubin, 2019).

The second limitation relates to the fact that the sample included only respondents aged 18–65 years; hence, we cannot claim that the model also generalizes to the segment of internet users aged more than 65 years. However, studies have suggested that these relationships should not be substantially different for this age group (Hernández et al., 2011; Hong et al., 2021; Law and Ng, 2016). Nevertheless, future studies could investigate the proposed model among older users and examine potential differences with respect to younger internet users.

From a substantive perspective, one may argue that the study explored the effects of only a specific form of self-efficacy, namely online

shopping self-efficacy. This approach is consistent with conceptual frameworks for self-efficacy which emphasize that self-efficacy should be measured at the same level and in relation to the same context as the action in question (Bandura, 1977). Nonetheless, future studies could further explore these issues by investigating how different types of self-efficacy, such as general, internet, or privacy self-efficacy, affect privacy concerns and e-commerce participation.

Finally, an interesting area for future research is to explore further the differences between consumers' personality types and their influence on the perceptions of privacy and self-efficacy in online shopping. Studies of consumer mental models (Westbrook, 2006; Wu et al., 2020) may be particularly valuable as they could provide insights into how consumers with different personalities structure their understanding of the online shopping process with respect to privacy.

6. Conclusion

This study provides original insights into the interplay among internet users' demographic characteristics and personality traits, their internet uses, online shopping self-efficacy, privacy concerns, and e-commerce participation. Although online shopping self-efficacy and breadth of internet uses were the strongest predictors of e-commerce participation, privacy concerns also played a notable role. The results also highlight the importance of online shopping self-efficacy as a mediator between consumers' demographic characteristics on the one hand and privacy concerns and e-commerce participation on the other. From a substantive perspective, the study suggests that the most feasible strategy for increasing e-commerce participation is to enhance internet users' self-efficacy. Furthermore, users with distinct personalities have different coping strategies related to privacy concerns and online shopping self-efficacy. Future exploration of these processes is warranted, as this could provide important new insights into the association

between self-efficacy and privacy concerns and how their relationship is shaped by individuals' personalities. Overall, our findings underscore the central role of online shopping self-efficacy in comprehensively understanding the antecedents and outcomes of privacy concerns in e-commerce.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jošt Bartol: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Vasja Vehovar:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Data curation, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Michael Bosnjak:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Andraž Petrovčič:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in PsychArchives at <https://doi.org/10.23668/psycharchives.5107>.

Appendix 1. – Items for the internet uses index

Table A1
Measurement items for internet uses.

#	Item text
1	Send or receive email
2	Used e-banking
3	Searched the Internet for information about products or services
4	I searched for health related information on the Internet, e.g. about injuries, illnesses, nutrition
5	I made a call or video call using a webcam via the Internet, e.g. using Skype, Viber, FaceTime, WhatsApp
6	Exchanged messages through programs like Viber, WhatsApp, Skype, Messenger, Snapchat
7	Sold products or services over the Internet, e.g. via bolha.com, e-bay.com, letgo apps
8	Read online news, online newspapers or online magazines
9	Sent messages, posted pictures, edited a profile, etc. on online social networks, e.g. on Snapchat, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter
10	Listened to music over the Internet, e.g. via web radio, YouTube, Deezer apps, Apple Music, Google Play Music, Spotify

Appendix 2. – Exploratory factor analysis of the five-factor personality traits model

To confirm the factor structure of the five-factor personality traits model, the EFA procedure performed by Donnellan et al. (2006) was followed. Namely, the principal axis factor (PAF) extraction method with a forced five-factor solution using varimax rotation was conducted. Orthogonal rotation was used because the Big Five personality factors measure five distinct facets of an individual's personality (John and Srivastava, 1999).

The factor analysis yielded expected results. However, one item predicted to load onto the conscientiousness factor ("Make a mess of things" – the item is reverse coded) had to be deleted because it had a low factor loading on conscientiousness (factor loading of 0.328), while it also loaded on the

neuroticism factor (factor loading of -0.351). Deleting this item also improved the reliability of the conscientiousness factor (from 0.671 to 0.691). The factor structure obtained after deleting this item was acceptable (Table A2), with no cross-loadings higher than 0.300. The reliability of the factors was also acceptable (Cronbach's alphas from 0.679 to 0.773).

Table A2
Factor loadings of the Big Five personality traits (weighted data).

Initial factor	Item text	E	N	O	A	C
E	I talk to a lot of different people at parties.	0.723	-0.081	0.045	0.109	0.101
E	I keep in the background. (R)	0.653	-0.237	0.096	0.192	0.039
E	I'm the life of the party.	0.615	-0.037	0.092	0.028	0.019
E	I don't talk a lot. (R)	0.600	-0.059	0.040	0.218	0.028
N	I have frequent mood swings.	-0.089	0.728	0.011	-0.043	-0.079
N	I get upset easily.	0.074	0.609	-0.045	-0.057	-0.007
N	I'm relaxed most of the time. (R)	-0.293	0.497	-0.057	0.055	-0.107
N	I seldom feel blue. (R)	-0.149	0.472	-0.023	0.068	-0.061
O	I have difficulty understanding abstract ideas. (R)	-0.007	-0.179	0.649	0.129	-0.012
O	I'm not interested in abstract ideas. (R)	-0.047	-0.032	0.601	0.158	-0.081
O	I do not have a good imagination. (R)	0.187	-0.081	0.584	0.092	0.085
O	I have a vivid imagination.	0.154	0.173	0.555	0.010	-0.056
A	I am not interested in other people's problems. (R)	0.011	-0.021	0.068	0.746	-0.051
A	I'm not really interested in others. (R)	0.181	-0.138	0.133	0.605	-0.027
A	I sympathize with other's feelings.	0.125	0.113	0.071	0.469	0.182
A	I feel others' emotions.	0.196	0.061	0.163	0.430	0.130
C	I like order.	0.033	0.044	0.020	0.012	0.776
C	I often forget to put things back in their proper place. (R)	-0.014	-0.206	-0.021	0.102	0.600
C	I get chores done right away.	0.123	-0.078	-0.064	0.046	0.592
	Eigenvalue	1.97	1.59	1.52	1.50	1.42
	Variance explained	10.4%	8.4%	8.0%	7.9%	7.5%
	Cronbach's alpha	0.773	0.686	0.692	0.679	0.691

Notes: E = Extraversion; N = Neuroticism; O = Openness; A = Agreeableness; C = Conscientiousness; (R) = reverse coded item. Factor loadings > 0.300 (in absolute terms) are in bold.

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